

Appendix A

Papers included in the literature review

	Paper title	Author(s)	Publication year
1	Evolutionary theory as a guide to socioscientific decision-making	Sadler, T. D.	2005
2	Integrating critical thinking about values into an introductory geoscience course	Yacobucci, M. M.	2013
3	On the legal issues of teaching evolution in public schools	Hermann, R.S.	2013
4	Lack of Evolution Acceptance Inhibits Students' Negotiation of Biology-based Socioscientific Issues	Fowler, S.R., Zeidler, D.L.	2016
5	Preservice science teachers' concerns and approaches for teaching socioscientific and controversial issues	Borgerding, L.A., Dagistan, M.	2018
6	Students' model-based explanations about natural selection and antibiotic resistance through socio-scientific issues-based learning	Peel, A., Zangori, L., Friedrichsen, P., Hayes, E., Sadler, T.	2019
7	Design-based learning for a sustainable future: student outcomes resulting from a biomimicry curriculum in an evolution course	Fried, E., Martin, A., Esler, A., Tran, A., Corwin, L.	2020
8	Exploring the rebuttal argument complexity of genetics in students through socio scientific issues using scientific writing heuristic (SWH)	Anisa, Widodo, A., Riandi, R., Muslim, M.	2020a
9	Analyzing socio scientific issues through algorithm	Anisa, A., Widodo, A., Riandi, R., Muslim, M.	2020b
10	Students' Argumentation in Science Lessons: How effective is Rebuttal Analysis Framework in Representing the Complexity of Classroom Argumentation?	Anisa, Widodo, A., Riandi, R., Muslim, M.	2022
